

ISic0964

Funerary inscription for Agathon

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 231

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.7 cm

Width 38.9 cm

Depth 1.8-2.3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 5-22 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Ἄπασα γῆα καὶ πλατοῖς ἀήρ
2. γενᾶ σοι θάνατε
3. ἔξαπίνης μου τὸ βρέφος ἤρπασε[ς ἦ]
4. τίς ἀνάκη εἰ γὰρ ἐγήρα, οὐχεί σον [ἦν]
5. ((chrison)) ἐγενήθη ὁ κύρις Ἀγάθων πῖρ(ὸ) ιε' ((chrison))
6. καλανδῶν Νοενβρίων ἡμέρα Κρό[νου]
7. ἔζη(σεν) μῆ(νας) ·ι· ἀπέθανε πῖρ(ὸ) ·ι·[-?] καλανδῶν Σεπτενβρ[ίων]
8. ἡμέρα Ἡλίου κυρία Ἀγάθη εἰρήνην Ἀγά[θωνι]

Apparatus

Translation (en)

All the earth and the air in its wide expanses begets you, o Death. On a sudden, you snatched away my

babe – or was there some necessity, for if he had grown old, would he not still have been yours?

Master Agathon was born the 15th day before the Kalends of November (= 18th October), on the day of Kronos; he lived 11 months; he died the tenth day before the Kalends of September (= 23rd August), on the day of the Sun. Lady Agatha, (grant) peace for Agathon!

Translation (it)

Tutta la terra e il vasto etere generano per te, o Morte. All'improvviso mi hai strappato via il

bambino, che necessità c'era? Infatti se fosse invecchiato, non sarebbe stato pur sempre tuo? Il

signore Agathon nacque quindici giorni prima delle calende di novembre (= 18 Ottobre) nel giorno di

Kronos. Visse undici mesi; morì dieci giorni prima delle calende di settembre (= 23 agosto) nel

giorno del Sole. Signora Agatha, (conceda) la pace a Agathon.

Commentary

The first four lines are in verse, and express ideas typical in pagan funerary inscriptions; the chi-rho symbols and the latter part of the text show that this is clearly a Christian epitaph. It is rare to mention the date of birth, especially in Greek Christian texts, and most parallels are for infants, as here. The closest parallel is the famous epitaph of Julia Florentina from Catania (now in the Louvre, Paris: Ma2994), an infant who was buried before the shrine of the martyrs, perhaps including St. Agatha. The significance of the final line of the text is debated, but it appears to be a prayer to Saint Agatha, in which case this provides the earliest contemporary evidence for the cult of St. Agatha at Catania, of similar date to that for St. Lucia at Siracusa in the epitaph for Euskia (Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inv.14600).

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